

Identifying Standard SKD/CKD and Automotive Manufacturing Development Stage in Ethiopia

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Abstract

Semi-Knock-Down (SKD) and Complete-Knock-Down (CKD) solutions have been widely accepted worldwide for export and import goods especially for automotive industry. The CKD kit ensures trade benefits and boosts technological capability for import substitutions. Duty at customs is high for products which are in the state of ready to use conditions where as the duty on SKD or CKD products imported from another country is lesser. Most domestic companies where the assembly cost is low and import cost is high prefer to buy product in SKD or CKD kits where as Complete-Built-Up (CBU) are not preferred technically and economically. This study focuses primarily on the basic concepts of assembly kit in Ethiopia, their benefits in tariff considerations, import substitution, technological transfer and other economic advantages. Secondly to analyzes basic problems on the understanding of these concepts to develop vehicle standard SKD and CKD in Ethiopia. In addition to this to highlight the automotive industry stage of development. The implementation of these concepts has great benefits in the size of job creation and import substitution rates which have impact on the economy. The investment for CKD in automotive industry requires greater finance when to compare machineries and equipment.

Keywords: Automotive, SKD, CKD, Tariff, Manufacturing, Assembly kit.

1. Introduction

The automotive sector is vast in terms of commercial and technical factors which require different types of assembling and vehicle body manufacturing facilities to produce finished products (White, 1979). Ethiopia is transforming from total car importer to domestic assembler to some extent and its automotive stage of development is compared and contrasted in Figure 1 in which Kenya and Myanmar are a little ahead of Ethiopia (Ohno, 2019). Information of products, suppliers, international quality service links and technology is still lagging behind which still gives space for CBU second hand cars in Ethiopia. The main problems in SKD and CKD shipments are related to tariff issues in a particular country and it should promote manufacturers over importers (Ohno, 2019).

Figure:01 Automotive industry development

According to Rob (2016), there are differences and inconsistencies in SKD and CKD definitions and standards worldwide as a result different countries may have different standards

require high capital investment. Knocked down strategy for a company should be carefully evaluated in order to decide with any kind of deal and the formula used to calculate the overall logistics cost of CKD is shown below (Malavolti, 2019) ;

$$\text{Cost of CKD} = \text{Cost of stock} + \text{Cost of warehouse} + \text{Cost of customer clearance} + \text{Cost of Shipping} + \text{Cost of customer clearance (Supplier)} + \text{Cost of stock (Supplier)} + \text{Cost of packing (supplier)} + \text{Cost of unpacking} \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

The finished bodywork is assembled in the country of destination and they are exported where complete disassembled of parts not required (Libor & Alan, 2008). According to the definition of Toni (2022), kit is not totally knocked down and SKD often refers to subassemblies that can be quickly and readily put together partially in another nation. CBU vehicles are those that arrive in a country ready to use with completely build. In the research paper of Yongwook (1987) and Tulder & Ruigrok (1998) each model change requires production line changes, re-tooling, and constant technological change. Some companies in Malaysia issued supplier development and localization program as well as locally produced parts initiated by the company with listed parts in different category (Abdullah, Lall, & Tatsuo, 2008). In conclusion, the common definitions of the three terms can be illustrated as shown below (Chemendy, 2018).

Figure:03 Automobile model kits

2.2 Automotive Manufacturing Processes

Automotive integrated manufacturing facilities consist of different shops or departments each with a special function with input resource delivered from outside suppliers. The body shop, paint shop, assembly shop and material logistics department are the five key departments that make up the general organisation of the assembly plant (Oumer, Atnaw, Cheng, and Singh, 2016). According to the paper by Sherry (2015) Mortimer (1987), KD parts are delivered to the production site by the car manufacturer or independent contract suppliers.

2.2.1 Chassis Fabrication

Generally there are different types of chassis according to the fitting of engine namely, Conventional chassis, Non-Conventional chassis, Full forward, Semi forward, Bus chassis, Engine in front and Engine at the center. Conventional type is also known as a non-load-carrying frame where as the non-conventional chassis is known as frameless chassis or unibody chassis

(Abernathy, 2012), (Brünger, Engler, & Hirsch, 2006) and (Selvamanikandan & Venkatesan, 2019).

Figure:04 Conventional and Non-conventional chassis

According to Bhise, (2012) and Hryciów, Wiśniewski, Rybak & Tarnożek, (2021), the bus chassis provides an increased floor space in the vehicle. Harr, (2018) described the automobile frame moves to component assembly areas where complete front, rear suspensions, different components and accessories are sequentially installed. Chassis is mostly imported from OEM in different forms. Every assembly task on chassis has provided assembly workers with the safest and most efficient tools available (Anazawa, 2021 and Aswicahyono & Kartika, 2010).

2.2.2 Stamping Process

Metal stamping is a sophisticated industrial process that uses a variety of metal shaping techniques to transform flat metal sheets into precise forms which is also known as pressing. The term "Body in White" (BIW) describes the parts of the car that have been welded together using various types of connecting methods. The parts included in the BIW are the cover, body, floor, and encon (Mortimer, 1987), (Selvamanikandan & Venkatesan, 2019), (Cooper, Rossie, & Gutowski, 2016), (Fu, Guang-Hong, Yang, Ma, Chen, & Zhu, 2022) and (Awatiger, 2020).

Figure: 05 BIW stamped parts (Yu-Kai Fu and et al, 2022)

The required shape is obtained by shaping the metal using different stamping techniques and model BIW stamped parts is shown in Figure 5 (Mortimer, 1987), (Cooper, Rossie, & Gutowski, 2016), (Fu, Guang-Hong, Yang, Ma, Chen, & Zhu, 2022) and (Asnafi, Shams, Aspenberg, & Öberg, 2019). Stamping is a common choice in the automotive sector due to its high productivity, affordable, capacity to provide exceptional strength, and cost-effectiveness at high production volumes (Cao, Kinsey, Yao, Viswanathan, & Song, 2001). Technically stamping is considered to be a net shaping process (Mortimer, 1987) and (Brünger, Engler, & Hirsch, 2006). The body of a vehicle is made up of several hundreds of stamped components which are joined together by spot welding and accurate production of the car body (BIW) is essential (Thiruvengadam, 2010) and (Chaturvedi & Kumar, 2019).

2.2.3 Body Fabrication

The process of fabricating bodies is extremely mechanized and most popular tools are used to create unibody chassis assemblies. The largest body component to which a multitude of panels and braces will subsequently be either welded or bolted together as it moves down the assembly line (Almeida, Diasa, Goncalvesa, Peschlb, & Hoffmeisterc, 2011). According to Sherry (2015),

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manually operated welding equipment is also used in less automated manufacturing facilities. The front and rear door pillars, roof, body and side panels are assembled in the same fashion with a high number of weld operations with a degree of great accuracy (Mortimer, 1987) and (Brünger, Engler, & Hirsch, 2006). Fully assembled parts are subsequently installed using pneumatically assisted tools (Almeida, Diasa, Goncalvesa, Peschlb, & Hoffmeisterc, 2011).

Figure:06 Car body fabrication

2.2.4 Vehicle Painting and Curing Ovens

Vehicles move into the paint shop after final body assembly. According to research paper of Pendar, Rodrigues, Carlos Pascoa, & Lima, (2022), the paint shop provides corrosion protection and attractive appearance to the BIW vehicle body. Primer coating operations in an automobile assembly plant are usually implemented in three stages (M. Mahajan, Varade, P. Mahajan & Patil, 2019).

Figure: 07 Layers in primer coating

The exterior body parts are thoroughly cleaned and inspected as it moves through a brilliantly illuminated white chamber to see any flaws (Pendar, Rodrigues, Carlos Pascoa, & Lima, 2022). The main purpose of painting is to prevent the BIW from corrosion and to provide desired shapes in style, texture and color. Different countries have their own vehicle painting standards and processes (Lovell, Higgs, & Deshmukh, 2006). Paints usage should be free of environmental hazard and most eco-friendly painting process should be used (Meschievitz T., Rahangdale Y., & Pearson R., 1995)

Curing ovens are directly or indirectly heated by various types of fuels and they are applied after the primer coat, base coat and the clear coats. Ovens are divided into multiple zones with the radiated heat dries the outer layer of the paint (Sherry, 2015) and (Akafuah, Poozesh, Salaimah, Patrick, Lawle, & Saito, 2016).

Figure:08 Flowchart of car painting process

2.2.5 Vehicle Interior Assembly and Car Mating

The painted body travels through the process where parts like instrumentation, wiring systems, dash panels, interior lights, seats, door and trim panels, headliners, radios, speakers, all glass (except the automobile windshield), steering column, wheel, body weather strips, brake and gas pedals, carpeting, bumpers and fascias are assembled. The automated lines facilitates a continuous process with a moderate speed which enables human operators to perform interior and door assembly tasks with the required level of safety (Mortimer, 1987) and (Brünger, Engler, & Hirsch, 2006). During mating the chassis assembly and body shell conveyor meet at final stage of production in which the shell is lifted from its conveyor fixtures and placed onto the frame to be bolted by assembly workers. The automobile travels down the assembly line to receive final trim components after auto mating of body shell and chassis White (1979) and (Brünger, Engler, & Hirsch, 2006). The majority of modern automobiles has a unibody construction in the middle of

the vehicle and supports various components in a half-frame configuration (Mortimer, 1987) and (Brünger, Engler, & Hirsch, 2006).

3. Material and Methods

3.1 Kit Production Network

The kit concepts mainly differ in terms of the degree of disassembly, partition, number of kits and the value addition. The automotive global production network clearly put the production strategy that determines the type of assembly sections established at the local production facility as well as in the sales country as shown in Figure 9 (Börold, Teucke, Rust, & Freitag, 2020) and (Schwede C., Song Y., Sieben B., Hellingrath B. & Wagenitz A., 2009).

Figure: 09 Strategies in global automotive production network

In SKD process description, the exporter collects and packs the parts in the SKD warehouse but the importer repacks the products in the local OEM factory. This process can be referred as SKD-packing-and-SKD-unpacking process (Börold, Teucke, Rust, & Freitag, 2020) and (Schwede C., Song Y., Sieben B., Hellingrath B. & Wagenitz A., 2009). Similarly under the CKD mode, the exporter has the control of technology, the factory organizational structure and

information flow. The operation point of view all CKD parts are subject to the CKD-packing before export in the exporter warehouse. The CKD kits are subject to the CKD unpacking before the assembly in the importer plant (Börold, Teucke, Rust, & Freitag, 2020) and (Schwede C., Song Y., Sieben B., Hellingrath B. & Wagenitz A., 2009).

3.2 CBU/SKD and CKD Tariff Conditions

Ethiopia is known for its high automotive tax rates which require various policies and amendments for car assembly from the CBU to SKD and then to CKD stage. Nigeria raised CBU tariffs to 70% for passenger cars and 35% for commercial vehicles while SKD tariff is 10%. CBU is taxed at higher than CKD which gives sufficient incentive for domestic assemblers. There is no distinction between passenger cars and commercial vehicles in Kenya’s tax structure as shown in the Figure 10 (Ohno, 2020) and (K.Ohno, I. Ohno, & Nagashima, 2018).

Figure: 10 Kenya’s automotive tax structure until 2019 (Ohno, 2020)

According to Ohno, (2020) and K. Ohno et al (2018), positive rates are applied for designated 17 automotive components but Kenya did not have an SKD definition as of 2019. The smaller tax gap is not economical to cover production cost and Japanese producers need at least

20-30% advantage in favor of SKD/CKD over CBU (Ohno, 2019), (Nogimori, 2020) and JETRO (2018). The duty rate for different automotive products and tariff code is tabulated from Ethiopian custom commission in accordance with different references from the Ethiopia Custom Guide, (2017), Ethiopian Customs proclamation, (No. 859/2014), Ethiopian Customs Tariff Book, (HS 2017) and Ethiopian HS Code Import Data. The tariff system for parts and accessories is seen clearly from Ethiopia’s automotive tariff structure as shown in the Table 1.

Table 1

HS code chapter 87 tariff description

Type of product	HS code Tariff code	Tariff description	Duty rate
Complete vehicle	8703 3219	Other vehicles, with compression ignition internal combustion piston engine(diesel or semi diesel)Of a cylinder capacity exceeding 1500cm ³ but not exceeding 2500cm ³Others	35%
Intermediate products	8706 0091	Chassis fitted with engines, for motor vehicles of headings 8701 to 8705OthersFor vehicle of heading 8703	10%
Parts and accessories	8708 4020	Gearbox and parts thereoffor industry assembly of (end-use condition) Vehicle of heading 8703	5%

3.3 Definitions and ambiguity

The main ambiguity for vehicle SKD/CKD kits arose due to the fact that all components are available in different chapters of the harmonized system and HS code. Most of the parts are found in Chapters 40, 68, 70, 73, 83, 84, 85, 90, 91 and 94. Concerns on Chapter 87 is that motor chassis fitted with cabs fall in headings 8702 to 8704 but not in heading 8706 about chassis fitted with engines for motor vehicles of headings 8701 to 8705. As stated on Ethiopian Customs Tariff Book (HS 2017) and Ethiopian HS Code Import Data, it is important to consider the exclusions as

well as the texts of headings 87.06 and 87.07 including note 3 in Chapter 87 when considering general HS code interpretation to sets of unassembled parts.

Table 2

Concerns on HS code chapter 87 subtitles

8706	Chassis with engine for tractors, motor vehicles for pass/good & special purpose
870600	Chassis fitted with engines, for the motor vehicles of headings 8701 to 8705. For the vehicles of subheading 870120 or heading 8702 or 8704
8707	Bodies (including cabs), for specific motor vehicles
870710	Bodies (including cabs) For the vehicles of heading 8703
870790	Other Bodies, for the Other Motor Vehicles

Each component in SKD and CKD kits are not specified clearly in order to insert additional clarifications in the subtitles. In the CKD case studies of Aswicahyono & Kartika (2010), some joint venture company are responsible to produce engine for commercial trucks and others to be imported from overseas companies as well as locally produced engine parts as shown in the Figure

11.

Figure: 11 Engine CKD part for firm 2

The actual collection of "parts" does not have to be sufficient to assemble complete vehicles according to the clarification and the "parts" can be assembled into an incomplete article that has the essential character of a complete or finished article as declared in Ethiopian Customs Tariff Book, (HS 2017) and Ethiopian HS Code Import Data.

3.4 Custom Duty and Product for Imported goods

The supply strategies and the growth of sales of the product or product life cycle from CBU to different KD products can be related with the market's maturity as a result the economic concept leads to a chronological order of the strategies (Schwede, Song, Sieben, Hellingrath and Wagenitz, 2009). The different import tax systems and facts in Ethiopia are shown in Table 3;

Table 3

Import tax in Ethiopia (Custom proclamation No. 307/2002, 570/2008, 610/2008 and directive no 18/2009), (Income tax proclamation No 286/2002 & Proclamation No. 285/2002), (Customs proclamation No. 622/2009) and (Customs tariff amendment No.1, 1996 edition)

S/N	Facts of taxes in Ethiopia	Remark
F1	The tax sequential orders are customs duty, excise tax, VAT, surtax and withholding tax. Taxes on imported goods are collected by Ethiopian Revenues and Customs Authority (ERCA).	ERCA collects customs duty based on the rules stipulated in the customs proclamation No. 622/2009.
F2	ERCA collects customs duty on a great variety of goods which can be classified into two categories. Depending on the primary purpose of the imported goods. Items for public, personal or non productive uses.	<p>Category 1</p> <p>It includes raw materials, semi finished goods, producers goods and import items for public use.</p> <p>Category 2</p> <p>It includes items such as consumer or finished goods imported for personal use.</p>

F3	Customs duty has 6 bands or groups of rates which are applied to imported goods. These bands of rates are 0%, 5%, 10% 20%, 30% and 35%.	The maximum is 35 percent of the CIF (Cost + Insurance + Freight) value of an imported item.
F4	According to the Customs Tariff, the maximum customs duty rate used to be 60 % of the CIF value of an imported item.	CIF(Cost + Insurance + Freight) value of an imported item
F5	Excise tax it is one of the most well known forms of tax in Ethiopia. It is a tax levied on selected goods such as luxury goods and basic goods. The minimum excise tax rate is 10% & maximum is 100%.	Excise Tax is also applied to goods which are considered hazardous to health and that may cause social problems.
F6	Excise tax has 10 bands or groups of rates at which excise can be charged. These band rates are 10%, 20%, 30%, 33%, 40%, 50%, 60%, 75%, 80% and 100%.	These rates are used to calculate the payable excise tax.
F7	In Ethiopia, VAT is levied at a flat percentage rate. To the exclusion of goods detailed in article 8 of the proclamation No. 285/2002 and goods exempted from VAT by the directive issued by the Ministry of Finance and Economic Development.	VAT is levied on every imported item. Importers are liable to pay 15 percent of the sum of cost, insurance, freight, customs duty and excise tax.
F8	Automotive techs are not included in the type of goods or services exempted from payment or VAT except the supply or import of fuel gas. It is stated at “Circular Ref. No. Am3/16/28/227.	The law that allows exemption of goods and services from payment of VAT for the supply or import of fuel gas.
F9	Surtax is the fourth of the five taxes imposed on import items. Surtax was introduced in the Ethiopian tax system on April 9, 2007. The council of Ministers issued a regulation to levy 10 percent surtax on imported goods.	Ten percent of the sum of cost, insurance, freight, customs duty, excise tax, and VAT is the base of computation for surtax on all goods imported into the country.
F10	There are items and services which are exempted from payment of surtax. Fertilizer, Petroleum, lubricants and motor vehicles.	Motor vehicles for freight and passenger and other special purpose motor vehicles.
F11	Withholding tax is not a tax in the traditional sense. Goods imported by the following individuals and firms are exempted from the 3 percent withholding tax imposed on commercial import items.	The amount collected on imported goods shall be three percent of the sum of cost, insurance and freight

		(CIF value). Auto tech is not included in this privilege.
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From customs proclamation No. 622/2009 and Customs tariff amendment No.1, (1996 edition), the formula for calculating customs duty and other taxes in Ethiopia are shown below;

	DPV= cost + Insurance + Freight.....	2
	DPV x CUDU = A.....	3
	(DPV+A) x EXTA = B.....	4
	(DPV + A + B) x VAT = C.....	5
	(DPV + A + B + C) x SURTAX=D.....	6
	DPV x WHT = E.....	7
	Total Payment = A + B + C + D + E.....	8

Where

DPV = Duty Paying Value; CUDU = Customs Duty Rate; EXTA = Excise Tax Rate; SURTAX = Surtax; WHT = Withholding tax

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Basic Standards Identified for SKD and CKD

Basic standards are required in the tax related issue and should be clearly put with clarifications as a result the Ethiopian standards (recommended) for SKD and CKD automotive products or categories is tabulated in Table 4,5,6 and 7 below. The SKD/CKD parts and production methodology differs from company-to-company, permission of OEM, manufacturers' company standard which is compatible with specific types of vehicles. SKD/CKD standards are summarized

for vehicle types categorized as LMV, MMV and HMV for different models are described in the tables below.

Table 4

Vehicle parts for standard SKD/CKD category (Engine)

Vehicle type	LMV, MMV and HMV	
KD type or form	SKD	
Engine	From OEM for SKD parts	
LMV, MMV and HMV Except for Bajaj and motor cycles	Full engine kit fixed on car chassis	Fittings and mechanical hardware
	Assembly manuals	Electrical harness
	User instructions	Fuel system pipe connection
	Basic drawings	Cooling system assembly
KD type or form	CKD	
Engine	From OEM to CKD parts	
It is for LMV, MMV and HMV Except for Bajaj and motor cycles Note: Low Motor Vehicle = LMV= Car, Jeep, Minivan, etc Medium MV = MMV= Tempo, bus, mini truck, etc High MV = HMV= Truck, trailer, container, tractor, multi-axle bus	Separate engine kit in box	Disc assembly clutch
	Engine is not fixed on chassis or airframe	Cover assembly clutch
	Assembly manuals	Fly wheel
	User instructions	Bracket mounting
	Basic drawings	Cushion rubber
	Engine testing instructions	Stopper
	Defect troubleshooting manuals	Alternator
	Ground support equipments	Starter motor
	Radiator	Manifold exhaust rear/front
	Oil pump	Fan
	Water pump	Inlet manifold
	Air filter & Oil filter	Cover assembly & Cover rocker assembly
	Battery	Fitting and mechanical hardware
	EGR valve and Catalyzer	Harness and Engine mounts

Table 5

Vehicle parts for standard SKD category (Car body)

Vehicle type	LMV, MMV and HMV	
KD type or form	SKD	
Car body	From OEM for SKD parts	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Main body (Body shell) + chassis unpainted ▪ All basic parts are supplied unassembled (LMV) (MMV and HMV) 	

<p>It is for LMV, MMV and HMV Except for Bajaj and motor cycles</p> <p>Note:</p> <p>Low Motor Vehicle = LMV= Car, Jeep, Minivan, etc</p> <p>Medium MV = MMV= Tempo, bus, mini truck, etc</p> <p>High MV = HMV= Truck, trailer, container, tractor, multi-axle bus</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Car chassis without body parts but engine, gearbox, wheel/ tire, steering, drive train, suspension/dumper, seats, batteries, exhaust system, control parts supplied unassembled (MMV and HMV) ▪ All electrical wiring installed with lights ▪ Car body parts painted for LMV 																																																												
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Table 6

Car body CKD manufacturing requirements

CKD tasks

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Main body (Body shell) + chassis unpainted ▪ Unassembled chassis or main body ▪ Car chassis without body parts but engine, gearbox, wheel/ tire, steering, drive train, suspension/dumper, seats, batteries, exhaust system, control parts supplied unassembled (MMV and HMV) ▪ All electrical wiring uninstalled ▪ Car body parts fully not assemble, unpainted and not glazed ▪ Some component customized locally
Related to chassis
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Without leaf spring ➤ Without differential/axel parts ➤ Without suspension joints ➤ Without axle longitudinal link supports ➤ Without inner cross members and brackets ➤ Unassembled brake and suspension components

Table 7

Vehicle parts for standard CKD category (Car body)

Vehicle type	LMV, MMV and HMV		
KD type or form	CKD		
Car body	From OEM for CKD parts		
It is for LMV, MMV and HMV Except for Bajaj and motor cycles Note: Low Motor Vehicle = LMV= Car, Jeep, Minivan, etc Medium MV = MMV= Tempo, bus, mini truck, etc High MV = HMV= Truck, trailer, container, tractor, multi-axle bus	LMV	MMV	HMV
	All car body SKD	All car body SKD components	All car body SKD
	Body sides, roof and floor	Body sides, roof and floor	All car body SKD
	Fully disassembled body	Disassembled (loose) chassis	Body sides, roof and floor
	Disassembled body parts	All materials supplied loose for	All materials supplied
	Disassembled doors, handle	Disassembled doors, handle and	Disassembled (loose)
	Full logistics with assembly line is required	Full logistics with assembly line is required	Disassembled doors, handle and locks
		Full logistics with assembly line is required	Full logistics with assembly line is required
Required equipments for CKD			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Welding guns, Jigs, Templates, ▪ Metrology Equipment (3-D measuring machines), etc. ▪ Conveyors, paint tanks, paint booth, ▪ Drying oven, etc. ▪ Wheel alignment tester, ▪ Turning radius tester and Shower testing ▪ Head light tester, ▪ Side slip tester, ▪ Speedometer tester, Brake dynamometer and 			

4.2 Stages of Development for Domestic Assembling Companies in Ethiopia

The development stage of different domestic vehicle companies for light vehicle, bus, truck and trailer assembling as well as manufacturing are assessed as per to 2019 data and the current five years data will be required to further filter the respective assessment but the stage is mostly at CKD. Table 8 for light vehicle, Table 9 for buses, Table 10 for trucks and Table 11 for trailer fabrication companies are tabulated below to assess their developmental stage in SKD/CKD strategies.

Table 8

Light vehicle assembling companies

S/N	INDUSTRY	Stage of development	
		SKD	CKD
1	Abay technical and trading sc.	✔	✘
2	Belayab motors plc	✔	✔
3	Bishofitu automotive industry	✔	✔
4	JIN BEI motors plc	✔	✔
5	Marathon motors engineering plc	✔	✔
6	Mesfin industrial engineering plc	✔	✔
7	Tamrin international trading plc	✔	✘
8	Yangfan motors plc	✔	✔

Table 9

Bus assembling companies

S/N	INDUSTRY	Stage of development	
		SKD	CKD
1	Ada bus assembling and steel engineering	✔	✘
2	Bishofitu automotive industry	✔	✔

Table 10

Truck assembling companies

S/N	INDUSTRY	Stage of development	
		SKD	CKD
1	Bishofitu automotive industry	✔	✘
2	Frankun ET automotive engineering plc	✔	✘
3	NA metal industry and engineering	✔	✘
4	AMCE(Automotive manufacturing of Ethiopia)	✔	✘
5	Mesfin industrial engineering	✔	✘

Table 11

Trailer fabrication and assembling companies

S/N	INDUSTRY DESCRIPTION	Stage of development	
		SKD	CKD
1	Abenco general construction industry and trading plc	✔	✘
2	Alami industrial engineering	✔	✘
3	AMCE (Automotive manufacturing company of Ethiopia (sc.))	✔	✘
4	Ami metal engineering	✔	✘
5	Asnake engineering	✔	✘
6	Belaynehe Kindie metal Engineering complex	✔	✘
7	Bridge metal & wood shop business plc	✔	✘
8	Dagim Kennedy general trading plc	✔	✘
9	Fasil Mesfin Derso manufacturing	✔	✘
10	Frankun ET automotive engineering plc	✔	✘
11	Habtom G/Egziebher Woldehawaryat	✔	✘
12	HH engineering plc	✔	✘
13	KG Engineering	✔	✘
14	Kifle Mekonene importer trade in iron & steel manufacturing	✔	✘
15	Maru metals industry plc	✔	✘
16	Mesfin industrial engineering plc	✔	✘
17	NA metal industry and engineering	✔	✘
18	Nehemiah engineering plc	✔	✘
19	NKG Engineering	✔	✘
20	Ocfa metal manufacturing plc	✔	✘
21	Rahel Dagnachew Gelaye	✔	✘
22	Tsehay industries sc.	✔	✘

From the above table, we can conclude that Ethiopia’s automotive development stage is mostly on SKD/CKD strategy and the import substitution or technological specialization is only on some body parts of vehicle types. Generally Ethiopia is in the second automotive manufacturing stage which is similar to the JICA report on automotive industrial development stage for Africa as shown below (FRN 2015 Report).

Figure: 12 Automotive manufacturing stages

5. Conclusion

In this study it is revealed that the value chain of interconnected global market system shows the importance of automotive manufacturing development with higher foreign investors’ and OEM role in this sector. The study identified clearly the following significance for assembling and manufacturing of auto vehicles in Ethiopia;

- Perform relevant research studies on SKD/CKD concepts practically which is functional in different countries and CKD related tariff system encouraged by other nations.

Collection of annual market data in SKD/CKD for all vehicle types in auto manufacturing areas in Ethiopia and the impact of tax rates. Review highlights for custom classifications and their gap in fulfilling the CKD tariff systems

- Clearly identify items to be manufactured domestically for all types of vehicles in order to promote the import substitutions. Auto domestic parts production capability study should be undertaken to restrict import of these parts and promote the manufacturers.
- Revise the established standard for SKD/CKD kits for automotive industry in all types of vehicle models annually. All the prepared documents should be revised side-by-side with the assemblers for its effectiveness or gaps in production.
- Import and excise duties for completed built-up and complete knocked-down vehicles should be promising in order to prohibit imports of used commercial vehicles, their parts, components gradually. Promising incentives should be provided for critical and high value-added parts and components.
- The custom and tariff issues should encourage strategic partnership between globally branded manufacturers (OEM) with domestic investors which enhance the competitiveness and effective technological transfer.
- Complete implementation of vehicle-type and component approval as well as vehicle end-of-life policy should be introduced by the Ministry of Transport for all types of vehicle imported to Ethiopia.
- The Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation should introduce and enforce mandatory standards for vehicles, their parts and components operational nationally.

- Relevant federal offices related to natural resources and environment should establish a clear roadmap for fuel, lubricants and paints standards used in vehicle operation, maintenance as well as manufacturing.

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